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ELECTRICITY MARKET AND POWER FLOW SERVICES FOR DYNAMIC MARKET SIMULATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The share of renewable generation is increasing all around the globe. This is leading to an increased need for designing new electricity markets that are suited to the new reality. Simulation is widely used to experiment and analyze the potential impacts of new solutions, such as novel electricity market designs. This paper presents the Electricity Market Service (EMS) and the Power Flow Service (PFS). The EMS is capable of simulating several electricity markets, namely EPEX SPOT market, MIBEL's day-ahead and intraday markets, Nord Pool day-ahead market. This service is easily integrated with other modules and relies on JSON inputs to execute the electricity markets, supporting different types of offers, namely block offers, flexible offers, and complex conditions. The results are also presented in JSON, including the general market results, as well the results by player. The PFS is responsible for creating electricity networks and evaluating them, according to the market results from the EMS. This paper presents a detailed description of how both systems work separately and in sync and how the connection to the external system can be accomplished. A case study involving the MIBEL market, using real players and offers data, based on a real power network from Portugal is presented.

Keywords: EMS, PFS, market

1 INTRODUCTION

The EMS and PFS were developed within the scope of TradeRES (TradeRES – Tools for the Design and Modeling of New Markets and Negotiation Mechanisms for a ~100% Renewable European Power System) [1], an innovative project that aims to meet the needs of society with an almost 100% renewable energy system, which is financed by the European program to support research and innovation, Horizon 2020 (H2020).

Due to the energy policies and objectives defined by the European Union (EU), as well as a growing concern with the environmental and climatic impacts of finite energies, the use of renewable energies begins to assume high importance [2, 3]. In this sense, the existence of renewable energy markets becomes necessary, allowing not only the purchase and sale of energy between companies but also between citizens, who can, this way, participate as buyers and sellers [4, 5]. Therefore, the existence of a tool capable of simulating the main renewable energy markets and responding to the needs that arise in this context becomes necessary. On the other hand, it is necessary to verify if the results obtained from these markets are valid according to the electrical network the players are inserted into [6].

For these reasons, this paper presents the implementation of the Electricity Market Service (EMS) and the Power Flow Service (PFS). The EMS is capable of simulating the main electricity market, such as the EPEX SPOT market, the MIBEL's day-ahead, and intraday markets, and the Nord Pool day-ahead market, as well as the symmetric and asymmetric pools. On the other hand, the PFS allows the definition and evaluation of electric networks, considering the loads associated with each bus.

Figure 1 - Flow of information in the EMS

Figure 2 - Flow of information in the PFS

After this introductory section, Section 2 features an explanation regarding electricity markets. Section 3 and 4 present an overview of the EMS and the PFS and Section 5 a study case involving both services. Finally, Section 6 concludes the most important aspects of this article. Figures 1 and 2 illustrate the flow of information in the EMS and PFS, respectively.

2 MARKETS

2.1 European Power Exchange SE

The European Power Exchange (EPEX SPOT) SE is an organization, headquartered in Paris, France, that allows energy producing companies or consumers to exchange energy. The company was created in 2008 due to the emergence of an increase in SPOT energy activities and has members in Amsterdam, Berlin, Brussels, London, and Vienna [7].

There are also two types of offers in this market, period and block offers [8]. While period offers are offers presented in a period, that is, one hour, block offers refer to offers that may be present in several periods. For a transaction of the latter type to take place, all the offers present in a block must be accepted, as otherwise everything is rejected.

2.2 Iberian Electricity Market

The Iberian Electricity Market (MIBEL) is an initiative that comes from the Governments of Portugal and Spain with the main objective of integrating the electricity system of both countries and began in 2007 [9].

The MIBEL has, like the EPEX SPOT SE market, a Day-ahead market with similar functionality. The difference lies in the type of offers that can be made in this market. Period orders remain, while block orders no longer exist. Complex conditions also arise, which are restrictions imposed by players that allow them to abandon a session or a period of a market if they are not complied with. In the case of the Day-ahead market, the complex conditions available are [10]: indivisibility, charge gradient, minimum income, schedule stop.

In addition to the day-ahead market, MIBEL also has an Intraday market used as a complement to the first one to adjust previously agreed values. The intraday market counts the participation of day-ahead players who did not have the opportunity to trade all the energy due to some type of restriction. In this scenario, any type of player can buy or sell energy, unlike what happened in the day-ahead market, where an individual only bought or sold. This market is similar to the MIBEL Day-ahead, except for the complex conditions that are [10]: charge gradient, minimum income, maximum payments, complete acceptance in all periods of the first tranche of the offer, complete acceptance in each period of the first tranche of the offer, minimum consecutive hours with full acceptance of the first tranche of the offer, maximum power.

2.3 Nord Pool

Nord Pool is an electricity market operating in the Nordic, Baltic, Western, and Central Europe regions, and the United Kingdom, in the case of its day-ahead market [11].

This type of market, again, is related to the next day and deals with three different types of offers [12]: single hourly orders, block orders, and flexible orders.

Single hourly orders correspond to buy and sell orders equivalent to those already defined in the EPEX SPOT SE and MIBEL markets, the period offers.

Block orders correspond to bids to buy or sell energy defined by the player with the price and the consecutive periods when this applies, with a minimum of 3 periods being mandatory.

Flexible orders represent energy sales offers that can be exchanged at any time in the session, meaning there is no need to indicate periods as in the block orders.

3 EMS OVERVIEW

The EMS is a web service that simulates electricity markets, receiving a JSON input, with information regarding the players and their bids for each one of the periods of the session, as well as other types of offers, namely block offers/orders of the EPEX SPOT and Nord Pool markets, flexible orders of the Nord Pool market and complex conditions of the MIBEL market. The result of the simulation is presented in JSON and shows the amount of energy and monetary values traded for each period globally and for each one of the players that took part in the market.

This web service was built using Eclipse Jersey, which is a REST (Representational State Transfer) framework that allows the implementation of a JAVA API for RESTful Web Services (JAX-RS). This service is available for public use at [13] and represents a flexible and easy way of executing electricity markets, useful not only for real cases simulation but also for learning the workings of these electricity markets. Besides, this service provides the validation schemas used to validate the inputs for the execution of the markets, does not require the installation of any software, and is very easily integrated with other applications.

By being such an important tool to simulate electricity markets, the EMS possesses a web page where all information regarding markets and available requests is available. This web page makes the use of such service very easy to understand, having, inclusively, a section where it is possible to execute electricity markets in real-time. In that section, changeable inputs examples are provided to help users understand the required elements to simulate a market, but they are not mandatory. The user can always build a different input and use it, as long as it is valid with the correspondent schema. This page was built using Angular, a framework capable of creating single-page applications (SPA) that possesses several libraries and examples that make its use simple. This web page is available to the public and can be found at [14].

4 PFS OVERVIEW

The PFS is a web service built with Django, that utilizes the *pandapower* library [15] to define and evaluate electrical networks. The *pandapower* consists of an open-source python tool capable of analyzing distribution and transmission systems [16] by using the power flow analysis to obtain the voltages at the buses, as well as the line flows and the system losses [17]. This service allows several types of requests using both JSON and Excel as input and output and allowing the definition of every element of an electrical network, as long as it exists in the *pandapower* library. The schemas built to validate the inputs of this service also allow different types of power flow algorithms, so that the user can choose the one that applies better to the scenario that needs to be tested. At last, the result type (JSON or Excel) can also be configured in the input, so that the user can choose the one that he is most comfortable with. This service provides several types of requests, such as the definition and evaluation of a network, the evaluation of a saved network with new buses' loads, and the retrieval of both the validation schemas for each one of the requests and the saved networks. This consists of a very flexible and fast way of evaluating electrical networks, not requiring any programming knowledge and permitting its integration in other applications and tools.

Just like was described for the EMS, the PFS also has a web page where all the requests are described allowing new users to understand the workings of the service. The web page also provides the schemas used for input validation, as well as an input example for each one of the different requests. The user can easily use these inputs, change them and evaluate networks or just simply create a new input from scratch and use it, both work perfectly using the web page or the service directly. This web page was built using Vue, which is a framework very useful in the creation of SPAs.

5 CASE STUDY

This case study is based on a scenario involving a 24 periods session with real players offers for all the periods of this MIBEL market session where 5 of the players are buyers and 4 are sellers. This scenario happens in the day-ahead market and because of that, only sellers present complex conditions. Seller 1 sets his minimum income with a total value of 1.000.000,00€ and value per MWh of 5.0€ with no scheduled stop, while Seller 2 sets the indivisibility condition to true.

Figure 3 presents the demand and supply of this scenario, as well as the market price for each one of the periods of the session.

Figure 3 - Available/required energy and market price in each session period

Analyzing now figures 4 and 5, it is possible to observe that complex conditions expressed had gigantic effects on the amounts of energy transacted, especially in the first period and from the eighth to the twenty-fourth period.

This is justified by the fact that seller 1 is removed from this session and seller 2 from periods one and eight to twenty-four, which is shown in Figure 5, where there is a high reduction in the offers in some periods.

Seller 1 is removed from the session due to the minimum income condition, which means that this failed to reach the minimum amount of 1000000€ profit that was defined, while seller 2 is removed from the aforementioned periods due to the condition of indivisibility, that is, it was not able to transact all the energy it had defined for the period.

Note also, in the three figures, that there are several periods in which the market price is set at 0€. These values occur because in these periods it was not possible to transact any energy due not only to the players being removed but also because there was no agreement between the remaining buyers and sellers.

Figure 4 - Required/satisfied energy and market price in each session period

Figure 5 - Available/satisfied energy and market price in each session period

Seller 3 is an energy aggregator, who has to manage several local networks, in particular the one shown in figure 6, which was taken from the *pandapower* library.

For this scenario, considering the original loads present in the network, the results obtained were valid with all buses' voltages being between 0.95p.u. and 1.05p.u., while the lines' loading percents never went above 20%. But there is a problem. Recently, some of the households require loads with bigger power loads, which means that new values have to be evaluated regarding the same network presented in figure 6.

Buses 3, 8, and 9 had their loads increased to 0.05p.u. from 0.0051p.u., while bus 10 had its load increased to 0.09p.u. from 0.0051p.u.. Using the PFS to calculate the power flow of the network with these new loads, the result was that the network was not valid, for the reasons presented in table 1.

Figure 6 - Local network (taken from [15])

Table 1 - Power flow results for new loads

Bus/Line	Reason
Bus 5	Below 0.95p.u. by 0.015p.u.
Bus 6	Below 0.95p.u. by 0.029p.u.
Bus 7	Below 0.95p.u. by 0.026p.u.
Bus 9	Below 0.95p.u. by 0.020p.u.
Bus 10	Below 0.95p.u. by 0.041p.u.
Bus 11	Below 0.95p.u. by 0.023p.u.
Line 8	Above 100% by 0.62%

6 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented two new web services to simulate electricity markets and evaluate electrical networks. Both these services constitute great tools to auxiliare in the tasks described, not only because of their simplicity of use but also because it requires no installations or any type of programming from the user, he only needs to understand JSON and Excel depending on the service or request he wishes to execute.

In the presented case study, it was possible to analyze the workings of these services, as well as some particularities of the MIBEL market and the power flow results for a local network, for different load values. In the case of the MIBEL market, it was observable that the complex conditions presented in the market had a deep impact, stopping the transactions of energy in several periods. In the case of the evaluation of the local network, the change in the value of the loads resulted in the network no longer being valid, which shows the importance of choosing correct values, in order to have a good working electrical network.

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